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Role of Government Schemes for Agriculture Development: An Analytical Study

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Introduction

Humans depend in many ways on ecosystems and their services for basic needs: agro biodiversity including genetic resources, clean water, shelter, food and raw materials. The central issue in agricultural development is the necessity to improve productivity, generate employment, and provide a source of income to the poor segments of population. The agriculture sector contributed 51.9 percent to India's GDP in 1950. Since then it has been on a downside and it currently stands at 13.9 percent. However, a change from an agrarian-centric economy to an industry-centric economy is inevitable with the advent of industries. Over the past few years, we have witnessed a number of positive initiatives emerge. Our government has introduced various schemes, programs and plans to benefit all the farmers. Such as:

1. Soil Health Card Scheme

Launched in 2015, the scheme has been introduced to assist State Governments to issue Soil Health Cards to all farmers in the country. The Soil Health Cards provide information to farmers on nutrient status of their soil along with recommendation on appropriate dosage of nutrients to be applied for improving soil health and its fertility.

2. National Mission for Sustainable Agriculture (NMSA)

NMSA is one of the eight Missions under National Action Plan on Climate Change (**NAPCC**). It aims at promoting Sustainable Agriculture through climate change adaptation measures,

enhancing agriculture productivity especially in rain fed areas focusing on integrated farming, soil health management, and synergizing resource conservation. NMSA as a programmatic intervention caters to Mission Deliverables that focuses mainly on conservation agriculture to make farm sector more productive and remunerative and climate resilient by promoting location specific integrated/composite farming systems.

Schemes under NMSA

- Rain-fed Area Development (RAD): RAD is being implemented by RFS Division.
- Soil Health Management (SHM): SHM is being implemented by INM Division
- Sub Mission on Agro Forestry (SMAF): SMAF is being implemented by NRM Division
- Soil and Land Use Survey of India (SLUSI): Being implemented by RFS Division
- Mission Organic Value Chain Development in North Eastern Region (MOVCDNER): Being implemented by INM Division
- National Centre of Organic Farming (NCOF): Being implemented by INM Division

3. Neem Coated Urea (NCU)

This scheme is initiated to regulate use of urea, enhance availability of nitrogen to the crop and reduce cost of fertilizer application. NCU slows down the release of fertilizer and makes it available to the crop in an effective manner. The entire quantity of domestically manufactured and imported urea is now neem coated. It reduces the cost of cultivation and improves soil health management.

4. Pradhan Mantri Krishi Sinchai Yojana (PMKSY)

It was launched on 1st July, 2015 with the motto of 'Har Khet Ko Paani' for providing end-to-end solutions in irrigation supply chain, viz. water sources, distribution network and farm level applications. PMKSY not only focuses on creating sources for assured irrigation, but also creating protective irrigation by harnessing rain water at micro level through 'Jal Sanchay' and 'Jal Sinchan'. Micro irrigation is to be popularized to ensure 'Per drop-More crop'. PMKSY adopts State level planning and projectised execution that allows States to draw up their own irrigation development based on District Irrigation Plans and State Irrigation Plans.

Components:

- Accelerated-Irrigation Benefit Program(AIBP): implemented by Ministry of Water Resources, RD & GR.
- PMKSY(Har Khet ko Pani): implemented by Ministry of Water Resources, RD & GR
- PMKSY (Watershed): implemented by Department of Land Resources.
- PMKSY(Per Drop More Crop - PDMC)

5. Paramparagat Krishi Vikas Yojana (PKVY)

It is implemented with a view to promote organic farming in the country. To improve soil health and organic matter content and increase net income of the farmer so as to realise premium prices. Under this scheme, an area of 5 lakh acre is targeted to be covered through 10,000 clusters of 50 acre each, from the year 2015-16 to 2017-18.

6. National Agriculture Market (e-NAM)

It provides e-marketing platform at national level and support creation of infrastructure to enable e-marketing. This innovative market process is revolutionizing agriculture markets by ensuring better price discovery. It brings in transparency and competition to enable farmers to get improved remuneration for their produce moving towards 'One Nation One Market'.

7. Micro Irrigation Fund (MIF)

A dedicated MIF created with NABARD has been approved with an initial corpus of Rs. 5000 crore (Rs. 2000 crore for 2018-19 & Rs. 3000 crore for 2019-20) for encouraging public and private investments in Micro irrigation. The main objective of the fund is to facilitate the States in mobilizing the resources for expanding coverage of Micro Irrigation. MIF would not only facilitate States in incentivizing and mobilizing resources for achieving the target envisaged under PMKSY-PDMC but also in bringing additional coverage through special and innovative initiatives by State Governments. An Advisory Committee has been set up to provide policy direction and ensure effective planning, coordination and monitoring of the Micro Irrigation Fund.

8. Agriculture Contingency Plan

Central Research Institute for Dry land Agriculture (CRIDA), ICAR has prepared district level Agriculture Contingency Plans in collaboration with state agricultural universities using a

standard template to tackle aberrant monsoon situations leading to drought and floods, extreme events (heat waves, cold waves, frost, hailstorms, cyclone) adversely affecting crops, livestock and fisheries (including horticulture). Total 614 district agriculture contingency plans are placed in the 'farmer portal' of the Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare,

9. Rain fed Area Development Program (RADP)

Rain fed Area Development Program (RADP) was implemented as a sub-scheme under Rashtriya Krishi Vikas Yojana (RKVY).

Aim

- To improve quality of life of farmers' especially, small and marginal farmers by offering a complete package of activities to maximize farm returns.
- Increasing agricultural productivity of rain fed areas in a sustainable manner by adopting appropriate farming system based approaches.
- To minimize the adverse impact of possible crop failure due to drought, flood or un-even rainfall distribution through diversified and composite farming system.
- Restoration of confidence in rain fed agriculture by creating sustained employment opportunities through improved on-farm technologies and cultivation practices
- Enhancement of farmer's income and livelihood support for reduction of poverty in rain fed areas and

10. National Watershed Development Project for Rain fed Areas (NWDPR)

The scheme of National Watershed Development Project for Rain fed Areas (NWDPR) was launched in 1990-91 based on twin concepts of integrated watershed management and sustainable farming systems.

Aim

- Conservation, development and sustainable management of natural resources.
- Enhancement of agricultural production and productivity in a sustainable manner.
- Restoration of ecological balance in the degraded and fragile rain fed eco-systems by greening these areas through appropriate mix of trees, shrubs and grasses.

- Reduction in regional disparity between irrigated and rain fed areas and;
- Creation of sustained employment opportunities for the rural community including the landless.

11. Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY)

PMFBY is an actuarial premium based scheme under which farmer has to pay maximum premium of 2% for Kharif, 1.5% for Rabi food & oilseed crops and 5% for annual commercial/horticultural crops and remaining part of the actuarial/bidden premium is shared equally by the Centre and State Government. One of the objectives of the scheme is to facilitate prompt claims settlement. The claims must be settled within two months of harvest subject to timely provision of both yield data and share of premium subsidy by the State Government.

12. Livestock insurance Scheme

It aims to provide protection mechanism to the farmers and cattle reapers against any eventual loss of animals due to death. The scheme also demonstrates the benefit of the insurance of livestock to the people and popularizes it with the ultimate goal of attaining qualitative improvement in livestock and their products.

13. National Scheme on Welfare of Fishermen

This scheme was launched to provide financial assistance to fishers for construction of house, community hall for recreation and common working place. It also aims to install tube-wells for drinking water and assistance during lean period through saving cum relief component.

14. Scheme on Fisheries Training and Extension

It was launched to provide training for fishery sector so as to assist in undertaking fisheries extension programmes effectively.

15. Gramin Bhandaran Yojna

Objective of this Scheme:

- Create scientific storage capacity with allied facilities in rural areas.
- To meet the requirements of farmers for storing farm produce processed farm produce and agricultural inputs.

- Prevent distress sale immediately after harvest by providing the facility of pledge financing and marketing credit by strengthening agricultural marketing infrastructure in the country.

Launch of Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana

To resolve the problem of unpredictable nature of farming and prevent farmer suicides in the country, the Government launched PM Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana in early 2016. It's a crop insurance policy with relaxed premium rates on the principal sum insured for farmers. Implemented with a budget of Rs 17,600 crore, this scheme will provide financial support to farmers and cover for their losses.

Conclusion:

(Budget 2019 with Special Reference to Farmers and Agriculture)

For farmers:

Rs 6,000 per year assured income support for small and marginal farmers. Farmers having up to 2 hectare of lands will get Rs 6,000 per year in three equal installments.

Interest subvention for farm loan takers: Farmers affected by natural calamities to get 2% interest subvention and additional 3% interest subvention upon timely repayment
2% interest subvention to farmers who pursue animal husbandry,

Fisheries jobs through Kisaan credit cards

Kamdhenu scheme for animal husbandry

Rural allocations

Rs 60,000 crore for MNREGA

Rs 19,000 allocated for construction of rural roads under Gram Sadak yojana

Presenting the interim Budget, interim finance minister Piyush Goyal announced a financial support package for marginal farmers that include direct cash transfer of Rs 6,000 per year in three installments'. In a bid to wooing the middle class, the ruling dispensation also announced a full tax rebate for the salaried class for those with an income of up to Rs 5 lakh.

We are living in a country where the cattle are worshipped as a goddess; about 60 percent of the population was banking on agriculture for their main source of income during the 1950s. Despite half of the population still continuing with the profession, the returns are low. By owning a fragmented land, effective irrigation and optimum usage of fertilizers for crops becomes difficult, thus resulting in lower yields. In India, more than two-thirds of the crops lack proper irrigational facilities, India being the second largest irrigated country after China.

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